

The Mantodea of Johan Fabricius

Kris Anderson

Abstract. Johan Fabricius (c. 1745-1808) described twenty-eight species of Mantodea. He used several private collections from across Europe as source material for his new species descriptions. Because of this, the locations of Fabricius' type specimens remain scattered. Some of his type specimens have been lost over time but many have survived. The present work provides a taxonomic analysis for each of the species that Fabricius introduced across five of his most influential texts concerning historical entomology.

Johan Christian Fabricius (c. 1745-1808) was a Danish naturalist who studied under Carl Linné. He was one of the first entomologists to utilize Linne's binomial nomenclature system, which he used to describe several thousand species that were new to science. To access such a large amount of new material for which to describe, Fabricius traveled throughout Europe to examine a number of private museums that were owned by affluent collectors. He was particularly interested in the collections of the London elite, whom he became personally acquainted with and whose homes he visited on several occasions for the purpose of curating the insects within their cabinets of curiosities.

We know from Hancock (2015: 153) that Fabricius was introduced by way of Solander to several notable collectors who resided in London. These affluent collectors included the likes of Joseph Banks, William Hunter, Dru Drury, Thomas Yeats and John Fothergill. Daniel Solander (c. 1733-1782), who was another former pupil of Linné, became the cataloging assistant at the British Museum in 1764 and also allowed Fabricius to review the public museum's holdings in their entirety. Fabricius visited London on at least seven different occasions between 1767 and 1787 to examine the insect specimens from the private collections of these high society contacts in addition to those specimens that were deposited within the British Museum.

The curatorial process that Fabricius employed can be deciphered from a careful chronological assessment of his work. During each successive trip to London, Fabricius visited the homes of the wealthy collectors whom he became acquainted with through Solander. As the private museums of these London elite expanded with continual acquisitions of new specimens, Fabricius had to revisit the same cabinets of curiosities several times to organize, identify, and describe the new species that had been accessioned. For those species that were determined to be previously unknown, Fabricius noted which collection he sourced the type material from as well as the collector, if such information was made available. For those species that he attributed to an earlier author, such as Linné, Fabricius included a comprehensive list of literature that pertained to that species but did not indicate which collection he analyzed the specimen from.

Of the many different collections that Fabricius sourced for his Mantodea material, three of them were the most prominent. These were the collections owned by Joseph Banks, William Hunter and his close friends Sehested & Lund.

Joseph Banks collection. Hancock (2015: 153) tells us that Joseph Banks (c. 1743-1820) was an extravagantly wealthy botanist who was accompanied by Daniel Solander on the 1768 voyage of the *Endeavour* to the South Seas under the command of Captain James Cook (c. 1728-1779). Banks reportedly purchased his way onto the ship in order to take part in the Royal expedition and brought with him his personal servant, Fothergill's servant, and an esteemed botanical artist, Sydney Parkinson. This small team of scientists collected and illustrated specimens throughout the various islands and mainland territories that were discovered during *Endeavour's* global journey. The *Endeavour* returned to London in 1772, bringing home with it some 35k specimens of plants and animals that were collected by Banks and his associates during the expedition. Fabricius was one of the first naturalists to examine the insects that were collected during this expedition.

Following the success of the *Endeavour* voyage, Banks sought to accompany Captain Cook on his next expedition. He redesigned and funded some personalized modifications to the HMS *Resolution*, the new ship that was to be used for the second voyage, in order to have luxurious comfort provided to him during the upcoming journey. When the ship was deemed unseaworthy due to his extravagant modifications, Banks removed himself from the voyage and sponsored others to attend in his stead. Banks was replaced by Johann Reinhold Forster and his son Georg Forster. These two scientists, with the aid of Anders Sparrman and Francis Masson, amassed large collections of plants and animals throughout the three-year voyage of the *Resolution* from 1772-1775. Collection locations during this second expedition included South Africa and Patagonia, where the team of scientists gathered several hundred specimens between them. Upon their return, the Forsters published several works about their voyage and the natural history observations and illustrations that they encountered. The family subsequently fell on financial hard times and sold their botanical drawings to Banks. The whereabouts of the Forsters' insect collection from this voyage are unknown but it seems likely that at least some of the specimens would have ended up with Banks, in addition to the illustrated plates that he had purchased from them. In either case, we know from Woodward (1894: 16) that Masson was at the direct employ of Banks as a plant hunter during this expedition so many of the specimens that originated from South Africa or Patagonia found their way into Banks' personal museum. Captain Cook embarked upon one additional voyage in the following years, culminating in his death during the third and final expedition. Banks also did not accompany Cook on this last voyage but he remained the benefactor of many of the specimens that were harvested by the other scientists whom he sponsored to attend. The efforts of these hirelings resulted in a massive amount of natural history objects that were deposited into Banks' personal museum over the following decades.

The Mantodea specimens that originated from India that are currently deposited within the Banks collection were provided by König. Johann Gerhard König (c. 1728–1785) was a student of Linné who lived in Denmark from 1759-1767. Skilled and educated as both a naturalist and physician, König joined the Tranquebar Mission in southern India as a medical officer to help service the natives who were living in Danish East India. In 1774, he took up a position as a naturalist for the ruling government of India. Four years later, in 1778, König was appointed naturalist for the British East India Company, where he remained until his death. While serving in this last capacity, König provided Banks with insect specimens that he had collected in southern India, many of which are believed to have been named and described by Fabricius (Dover 1922: 339).

In addition to those specimens from India, Fabricius described several Mantodea specimens from the Banks collection that reportedly originated from “Africa aequinoctiali” or Equatorial Africa, i.e. tropical/Sub-Saharan Africa. These specimens were provided by Smeathman from Sierra Leone. Henry

Smeathman (c. 1742-1786) was an English naturalist who was sponsored by Banks, Fothergill, Drury, Marmaduke Tunstall and the Duchess of Portland to collect natural history specimens in Sierra Leone between 1771-1775. Douglas (2008) informs us that Smeathman lived on an island just off the West African coast, where he married several local women and mounted many local expeditions to harvest specimens for his sponsors. Smeathman sent back to London several boxes of insect specimens throughout his residency in Sierra Leone, and these were then distributed among the private collections of his sponsors. Following the four years that he spent in Africa, Smeathman relocated to Barbados via slave ship and continued collecting specimens for his sponsors in the Caribbean before returning to England in 1779.

Hancock (2015: 157) documented that Fabricius visited Banks' home on several occasions during his seven trips to London to describe the insects that were continually being added to Banks' collection from the newly explored territories overseas. It was during these times that Fabricius would redistribute the duplicates that he found within Bates' collection to the collections of William Hunter, Dru Drury and Thomas Yeats, or in the case of larger series of matching specimens, into his own personal collection. Joseph Banks' insect collection remains in London and is currently a special part of the Natural History Museum. The Mantodea specimens within the Banks collection comprise just one drawer. There is a hand-written label positioned immediately below each specimen that indicates a species level determination and a reference to one of Fabricius' works.

William Hunter collection. William Hunter (c. 1718-1783) was an esteemed physician and a highly influential human anatomist who owned a massive collection of natural history objects that he kept within his home. Hunter did not personally collect these objects himself but rather had a network of collectors spread across the globe, many of them his former pupils, who harvested and collated objects of interest for him. Hunter routinely allowed specialists access to his cabinets to curate the specimens within their respective area of study with the eventual aim of turning his private collection into a public museum of learning. Hancock (2015: 158) informs us that Hunter's cosmopolitan collection differed significantly from those of his contemporaries, as it contained a considerable number of specimens from the New World. For example, Etienne Couderc, the co-owner of the Berg en Dal and Breukelerwaard plantations in 18th century Surinam, is known to have provided Hunter with insect specimens from South America.

Fabricius curated Hunter's insect collection during his multiple visits to London and used Hunter's cabinets as a primary repository for the duplicate specimens that he sourced from the collections of Joseph Banks, Thomas Yeats, Dru Drury and John Fothergill. As such, the Hunter collection contains many specimens that originated from the voyages of Captain Cook in addition to those from the former British colonies in the Caribbean and North America. William Hunter's collection was moved from London to the University of Glasgow in 1807, where it remains to this day.

Hancock (2015: 162) advised that Fabricius' *Species Insectorum* from 1781 was used by Matthew Baillie, Hunter's nephew and inheritor, to arrange Hunter's insect collection between 1783 and 1785— several years after Fabricius had curated the collection. Baillie created the handwritten labels himself and cross-referenced the page and species number from *Species Insectorum* with Hunter's specimens. However, during the more than two centuries that followed this labeling process by Baillie, several drawers within Hunter's cabinets reportedly underwent additional rearrangements by unknown persons where some specimens and labels were evidently lost. Zimsen (1964: 16) noted that both Graham Kerr and Robert Staig critically assessed the Fabrician types within the Hunterian Collection and experienced “considerable trouble and deplorable loss of time” locating the misplaced types and matching them with what could be found of Baillie's corresponding labels. As they were never attached to the individual specimens, Baillie's labels were first pinned above their corresponding specimens, then later removed, rearranged and gummed to the drawer itself, then removed and mounted once more above the surviving specimens that they were believed to correspond with. As a result, several of the surviving Mantodea

specimens within the Hunter Collection have no label at all and other labels have been assigned to specimens that they have no relation to. Additionally, many of the surviving Mantodea specimens that are currently deposited with the Hunter Collection were clearly never assessed by Fabricius and were evidently added after his final review of the collection in 1780, as they do not correspond to any of Fabricius' descriptions and the author made no mention of them.

Sehested & Tønder Lund collection. Niels Tønder Lund (c. 1749-1809) was a Danish zoologist and lifelong friend of Ove Ramel Sehested (c. 1757-1838), who was a prominent economist and administrator within the Danish government. The two of them were fascinated with collecting insects from an early age and studied natural history together under Fabricius. As they both became employed as civil servants later in life, they were stationed abroad by the state and were afforded the opportunity to continue collecting insects in foreign lands. As a result, their respective insect collections swelled with unique material. Fabricius had access to these collections and routinely assessed the material within. Sehested eventually integrated his personal collection into Lund's and the combined collection was deposited into the Zoological Museum in Copenhagen. Vilhelmsen (pers. com.) advised that these specimens were provided with typewritten labels after they were transferred to the current museum building in the early 1960's. During this same time period, Fabricius' personal collection from Kiel was integrated into the Zoological Museum in Copenhagen as a permanent loan. These specimens have handwritten labels that were created by a different curator at some point prior in the late 19th century.

There are several additional points to consider when reviewing Mantodea taxonomy as it relates to Fabricius:

1) Many of the species that Fabricius described originated from foreign lands and were sparsely represented among European collections. For this reason, whenever Fabricius came upon "duplicate" specimens within some of the larger collections that he curated, he distributed the matching specimens into different cabinets to safeguard against loss or damage. Thus, there are specimens of several syntype series that are still deposited in separate historical collections and, as an intended result of Fabricius' reallocation of specimens, many have survived.

2) Fabricius did not designate any type specimens among the taxa that he described. For those species that he described from a single specimen, the holotype is fixed by monotypy (ICZN Article 73.1.2). For those species that were described from a series of specimens, these are automatically designated as syntypes (ICZN Article 73.2).

3) Fabricius did not generate any labels for the specimens that he described from the cabinets of others. Various persons who curated Fabricius' material after his death generated labels of their own that were based upon the interpretation of Fabricius' published works. These labels were oftentimes not pinned to the specimen. Thus, in addition to the potential misidentification of specimens by others who created the labels, the labels themselves have suffered loss and mismatching.

With these points in mind, let us now turn to the Mantodea species that were established by Fabricius. They are as follows:

Figure 1: Nontypes of *Mantis bidens* (♂ left, ♀ right) with Baillie label pinned to drawer. Additional typewritten labels and circular cotype labels pinned to the drawer were provided by University of Glasgow for cataloging. GLAHM: 133914 & 133915 © The Hunterian, University of Glasgow 2023

-bidens. *Systema Entomologiae*, 1775: 277. Fabricius described *Mantis bidens* from a female specimen that he had analyzed from the Hunter collection. This specimen was evidently mounted with spread wings, as Fabricius detailed the coloration of the hindwings of this species within his original description. He reported that the holotype originated from “America”. Anderson (2021: 192) explained that this geographical designation, at least in the case of this particular specimen, refers to Jamaica. Anderson further argued that *bidens* is the same species that Drury described as *Mantis cingulata* in 1773 from a female specimen that was brought from Jamaica to England and received by John Fothergill. The female holotype from Fothergill’s collection that Drury described and had illustrated was also mounted with spread wings. It is believed that the *bidens* holotype and the *cingulata* holotype are one in the same.

As this species is precinctive to Jamaica, the provenance of the female specimen that Fabricius described as *bidens* is clear. How this specimen became part of Hunter’s collection is more speculative but there is some circumstantial evidence to support the claim that it came from Fothergill’s collection as a designated duplicate. We know from Drury (1773: 89) and Booth (2002: 225) that Fothergill sponsored one Roger Shakespear to collect plants, seeds and insect specimens from Jamaica for him. Hunter had no known contacts or collectors from this British colony. Hancock (2015: 153) further informs us that Fabricius had access to Fothergill’s collection and it is well documented that he redistributed duplicates found in others’ collections into Hunter’s cabinets. Thus, it is likely that Fothergill had received a series of Mantodea from Jamaica and that Fabricius redistributed some of the duplicate samples into Hunter’s collection.

The original series from Jamaica consisted of at least three males and two females. Two of the male specimens and one of the females had their wings spread. Fabricius seemingly took one of the spread males and the single spread female from this series and allocated these specimens into the Hunter collection. Males of this species have hyaline hindwings; the hindwings of the female are dark-colored. This salient difference prompted Fabricius to believe that these two specimens represented distinct species. Thus, he described the male as *hyalina* and the female as *bidens*— while being seemingly

unaware of Drury's earlier work by two years wherein the female specimen from Fothergill's collection had already been described as *cingulata*.

This hypothesis requires that Fabricius was unaware of Drury's *Illustrations of Natural History* publication from 1773, wherein the female *cingulata* specimen was featured. This work was not referenced by Fabricius in any of his own publications despite him being personally acquainted with Drury, so it remains possible that Fabricius was oblivious to the fact that the *bidens* specimen had already been described two years prior by his friend under a different name. Given the close gap of publication dates between the two authors, it is more plausible that Fabricius had actually described *bidens* first while the *cingulata* plate was being prepared by Drury but that Fabricius' work was delayed and was not published until later, which has been the case in several other incidents of 18th century taxonomy. In either event, Fothergill died in 1780 and the entirety of his collection was bequeathed to Hunter. So the female holotype of *cingulata* should be in the Hunter collection. As there are no surviving female specimens of either *cingulata* or *bidens* within the Hunter collection that have spread wings, whether these types are one in the same specimen cannot be confirmed, as they are both considered lost.

At present, there is a conspecific pair of *bidens* within the Hunter collection (Figure 1) with an accompanying label that is pinned next to the specimens that reads: "Mant. Bidens. Fabr. pag 350 No. 24." This label was created by Baillie and refers to the page and species number from Fabricius' *Species Insectorum*, where he republished the description summary. These specimens are believed to have been part of the original series from Fothergill's collection and were incorporated into the Hunter collection upon Fothergill's death. It was Fabricius who was responsible for integrating Fothergill's insect material into Hunter's cabinets but he was not known to have labeled any of these specimens. Thus, Baillie evidently found that these two specimens represented *bidens* and labeled them as such. In 1781, Fabricius republished the description summary of *bidens* within *Species Insectorum*, again in 1787 within *Mantissa Insectorum* and once more within *Entomologia Systematica* in 1793.

Pseudovates cingulata (Drury, 1773)
 Mantis cingulata Drury, 1773
 = *Mantis bidens* Fabricius, 1775

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-*cancellata*. *Systema Entomologiae*, 1775: 276. Fabricius described *Mantis cancellata* from a specimen that he had examined from the British Museum. The insect collection at the British Museum was initially formed by a private collection that was owned by Sir Hans Sloane (c. 1660-1753) – a renowned botanist and collector who bequeathed the extensive holdings of his cabinets to King George II upon his death in 1753. Sloane, a physician by trade and a Jamaican plantation owner by marriage, invested a great deal of his wealth into the acquisition of thousands of natural history objects from colonial settlers throughout the British Empire. The natural history objects from the British Museum were moved to the British Museum of Natural History in 1887, which later became known as the Natural History Museum. The *cancellata* holotype is believed to have been part of Sloane's original collection. Zimsen (1964: 615) documented that the holotype is presently lost. Fabricius republished the description summary of *cancellata* in *Species Insectorum*, wherein he continued to chart that this specimen originated from "Indiis". He revised the type location of this species to "India" within *Entomologia Systematica* from 1793. Roy (2004b: 118) declared that *cancellata* is *nomen dubium* but that it probably represents *Asiadodis squilla* (Saussure, 1869) from India.

Mantis cancellata Fabricius, 1775 *nomen dubium*

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-cordata. Supplementum Entomologiae Systematicae, 1798: 190. Fabricius described *Mantis cordata* from a specimen that he had examined from “Mus. Galliae,” which is presumably the Museum of Natural History in Paris. He documented the origin of this species as “Indiis”. Fabricius interchangeably used “Indiis” to refer to India or to the East/West Indies, thus the type location is uncertain in this case. There was no collector listed for this specimen and the holotype has not been located. In 1871, Saussure listed *cordata* within the genus *Deroplatys* Westwood, 1839 with no justification or comment. Kirby continued to include this species within *Deroplatys* in 1904, again with no comment. In 1917, Giglio-Tos raised a query regarding the status of *cordata*, stating that it is “perhaps not even a Mantis”. He expounded upon these sentiments in 1927 when he wrote: “Kirby placed this species among the species of the genus *Deroplatys*. However he did not know her. I therefore doubt that it is a *Deroplatys* and I even doubt whether it’s a Mantid.” This species name has been largely absent in modern academic literature pertaining to Mantodea but it remains commonly used within the hobbyist and citizen scientist community. According to Fabricius’ original description of *cordata*, the specimen that he examined had a pale brown head capsule with antennae measuring the length of the specimen’s body. He described the greenish pronotum as being heart-shaped with serrated lateral margins. The forewings were noted as also being green and measuring just half the length of the abdomen, whereas the hindwings were as long as the body and green as well. Lastly, Fabricius described the anterior legs with foliated femora. These characters are reminiscent of Phasmatodea but no presently understood species of any insect possesses the complete combination of characters as put forth by Fabricius. Thus, it is believed that Fabricius described a chimeric specimen— perhaps one that was composed of Mantodea and Phasmatodea parts that had been glued together, either haphazardly or intentionally. In either case, *cordata* certainly does not belong within *Deroplatys* and has doubtful application to any known taxa.

Mantis cordata Fabricius, 1798 **nomen dubium**

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Figure 2: Syntype of *Mantis fenestrata* ♂ with determination/reference label attached to drawer and collection locality label pinned to specimen. BMNH(E) #669479. Joseph Banks collection at the Natural History Museum in London

-fenestrata. Species Insectorum, 1781: 349. Fabricius described *Mantis fenestrata* from a male specimen that he had analyzed from the Banks collection. He listed the type locality of this holotype as “Africa aequinoctiali” (Sierra Leone). This specimen was presumably collected by Smeathman. The

holotype from the Banks collection has survived (Figure 2). The accompanying label reads: “Mant. Fenestrata F. Sp. Ins. n. 23,” which indicates the species determination and references the species number from Fabricius’ *Systema Insectorum*. There is a smaller label attached to the drawer bottom with “Type” written on it. These labels are of an unknown hand. In 1787, Fabricius republished the description summary of *fenestrata* within *Mantissa Insectorum* and again within *Entomologia Systematica* in 1793.

Figure 3: Syntype of *Mantis fenestrata* ♂ with missing Baillie label. Additional typewritten label provided by University of Glasgow for cataloging. GLAHM: 133741. © The Hunterian, University of Glasgow 2023

A second male syntype has been located in the Hunter collection (Figure 3) that was evidently part of the original series and reallocated by Fabricius. The Baillie label for this second syntype has been mismatched with a *Tenodera superstitiosa* specimen in a separate drawer (Figure 26).

Miomantis fenestrata (Fabricius, 1781)
Mantis fenestrata Fabricius, 1781

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Figure 4: Syntypes of *Mantis flabellicornis* ♂. NHMD67839, NHMD67840 & NHMD67841. Courtesy of Lars Vilhelmsen at the University of Copenhagen, Natural History Museum of Denmark Zoological Museum.

-flabellicornis. *Entomologia Systematica*, 1793: 16. Fabricius described *Mantis flabellicornis* from a series of three male specimens that he had analyzed from the Sehested & Tønder Lund collection. He listed the type locality of this species as “Tranquebariae” (now modern day Tharangambadi, India). The *flabellicornis* syntypes (Figure 4) remain within the Fabricius collection at the University of Copenhagen with a typed label that reads: “*Mantis flabellicornis* F. Ent. Syst. 2 1793 p. 16,” which indicates the species determination and references the page number from Fabricius’ *Entomologia Systematica*. This label was created when the Kiel and Copenhagen collections were integrated together in the 1960s. These specimens are actually males of *Gongylus gongylodes* (Linné, 1758) but due to the significant sexual dimorphism within this species, Fabricius believed that they represented a different species apart from Linné’s *gongylodes* that was described from a female and a nymph.

Gongylus gongylodes (Linné, 1758)
= *Mantis flabellicornis* Fabricius, 1793

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-grisea. *Entomologia Systematica*, 1793: 22. Fabricius described *Mantis grisea* from a male specimen that he had examined from the British Museum in London. He did not list a type locality for this species or a collector. The whereabouts of the holotype are presently unknown.

Gonatista grisea (Fabricius, 1793)
Mantis grisea Fabricius, 1793

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Figure 5: Holotype of *Mantis hyalina* ♂ with Baillie label pinned to drawer. Additional typewritten label pinned to specimen and red note/circular syntype label provided by University of Glasgow for cataloging. GLAHM: 133910 © The Hunterian, University of Glasgow 2023

-hyalina. *Systema Entomologiae*, 1775: 277. Fabricius described *Mantis hyalina* from a male specimen that he had analyzed from the Hunter collection. He reported that the holotype originated from “America” along with *bidens*. The type had previously been lost for many years, as Kerr (1910: 107) documented that “a bare pin accompanies the label” of this species during his review of the Hunter Collection. However, during subsequent curation of the surviving material, the specimen was rediscovered and matched with its Baillie label (Figure 5). This label reads “Mant. hyalina. Fabr. pag 349 No. 22,” which refers to the page and species number from Fabricius’ *Species Insectorum*, where he relisted the description summary. The holotype is believed to have been an original part of Fothergill’s collection. Drury may have very well reviewed this specimen while it was within Fothergill’s collection but chose not to describe or illustrate it, as he thought that it was not new to science, as opposed to the dimorphic female that he had “not seen it any where described”.

A recent review of The Hunter collection by the present author has led to the discovery of a second specimen of *hyalina* that has been mislabeled as *strumaria* Linné, 1758 (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Mislabeled nontype of *Mantis hyalina* ♂ with Baillie label pinned to drawer. Additional typewritten label provided by University of Glasgow for cataloging. GLAHM: 133902 © The Hunterian, University of Glasgow 2023

This specimen was found positioned within insect drawer H100 of the Hunter Collection beneath the Baillie label for *Mantis strumaria* –a species that is a member of the distinctive genus *Choeradodis* Serville, 1831. Placed in between the two *hyalina* specimens within this same drawer is a *Choeradodis* female that is without a label. It is unlikely that this second specimen of *hyalina* is a syntype, as Fabricius would not have redistributed into the Hunter collection more than one male from the original Fothergill series. Rather, this specimen was likely integrated into the Hunter collection as part of the Fothergill donation upon his passing. In 1781, Fabricius republished the description summary of *hyalina* within *Species Insectorum* and again in 1787 within *Mantissa Insectorum* and once more within *Entomologia Systematica* in 1793.

Pseudovates cingulata (Drury, 1773)
Mantis cingulata Drury, 1773
 = *Mantis hyalina* Fabricius, 1775

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Figure 7: Holotype of *Mantis lanceolata* ♂ NHMD67842. Courtesy of Lars Vilhelmsen at the University of Copenhagen, Natural History Museum of Denmark Zoological Museum.

-lanceolata. Supplementum Entomologiae Systematicae, 1798: 191. Fabricius described *Mantis lanceolata* from a male specimen that he had analyzed from the Sehested collection (prior to Sehested integrating his collection with Tønder Lund). Fabricius listed the type locality of this species as the “India orientali” (east India). The *lanceolata* holotype (Figure 7) remains within the Fabricius collection at the University of Copenhagen with a typed label that reads: “Mantis lanceolatus F. Ent. Syst. Suppl. 1798 p. 191,” which indicates the species determination and references the page number from Fabricius’ *Supplementum Entomologiae Systematicae*. This label was created when the Kiel and Copenhagen collections were integrated together in the 1960s into the first Zoological Museum, as evidenced by the alternate spelling of “*lanceolatus*” that was not of Fabricius.

Didymocorypha lanceolata (Fabricius, 1798)
Mantis lanceolata Fabricius, 1798

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Figure 8: Syntype of *Mantis lobata* ♀ with determination/reference label attached to drawer. BMNH(E) #669454 Joseph Banks collection at the Natural History Museum in London

-lobata. Species Insectorum, 1781: 350. Fabricius described *Mantis lobata* from two female specimens that he had analyzed from the Banks collection. He listed the type locality of this species as the “Cap. bon. sp.” (the Cape of Good Hope or modern day Cape Town, South Africa). The syntype from the Banks collection has survived (Figure 8). The accompanying label reads: “Mant. lobata Fabr. Sp. Ins. n. 28,” which indicates the species determination and references the species number from Fabricius’ *Systema Insectorum*. The author of this label is unknown.

Figure 9: Syntype of *Mantis lobata* ♀ with Baillie label pinned to drawer. Additional typewritten label provided by University of Glasgow for cataloging GLAHM: 133909 © The Hunterian, University of Glasgow 2023

The other syntype (Figure 9) remains within the Hunter collection, where it was evidently allocated by Fabricius as a duplicate. The accompanying Baillie label for this specimen reads “Mant. lobata Fabr. pag 350 No. 28,” which refers to the page and species number from Fabricius’ *Species Insectorum*. Both of the syntypes were likely collected by the Forster-Masson team during the first voyage of the *Resolution* but may have possibly been collected under the direct supervision of Banks himself during the voyage of the *Endeavour* when it stopped through the Cape of Good Hope. These female specimens were thought by

Fabricius to represent a distinct species apart from the sexually dimorphic males, which Linné described under *tricolor* in 1758. In 1787, Fabricius republished the description summary of *lobata* within *Mantissa Insectorum*. He again published the description summary of this species within *Entomologia Systematica* in 1793.

Harpagomantis tricolor (Linné, 1758)
Gryllus (Mantis) tricolor Linné, 1758
Mantis tricolor Linné, 1767
= *Mantis lobata* Fabricius, 1781

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-*lobata*. Supplementum Entomologiae Systematicae, 1798: 190. Fabricius used the same binomial *Mantis lobata* to describe an entirely different species that he had examined from Bosc's collection. He listed the type locality of this species as "Cajennae" (Cayenne, French Guiana). Zimsen (1964: 16) wrote that Louis Augustin Guillaume Bosc d'Antic (c. 1759-1828) was "an intimate friend of Fabricius" who was an avid collector of insects. Fabricius reportedly described many insects from Bosc's collection during his stays in Paris. A large portion of Bosc's collection was eventually deposited at the Museum of Natural History in Paris after his death but many of Fabricius' types that were included therein have not survived the years. The holotype of this species has yet to be recovered and it is believed to be lost or destroyed.

Mantis lobata Fabricius, 1781 and *Mantis lobata* Fabricius, 1798 are primary homonyms, given that the author used the same species-group name to describe two different taxa that were both originally combined under *Mantis*. The senior homonym from 1781 has not been used as a valid name after 1899, therefore meeting condition 23.9.1.1 of ICZN article 23.9 reversal of precedence standard. However, condition 23.9.1.2 of this same article has not been met. This condition requires that "the junior synonym or homonym has been used for a particular taxon, as its presumed valid name, in at least 25 works, published by at least 10 authors in the immediately preceding 50 years and encompassing a span of not less than 10 years." *Mantis lobata* Fabricius, 1798 (the junior homonym) has been used as the presumed valid name for a species of *Vates* Burmeister, 1838 in only 11 works that were published by 18 authors since 1973: Terra (1995: 59), Cerda (1997: 26), Jantsch (1999: 99), Ehrmann (2002: 364), Agudelo (2004: 56), Agudelo, Lombardo & Jantsch (2007: 128), Greener & Rutherford (2014: 41), Svenson, Medellín & Sarmiento (2016: 237), Roy (2019: 68), Rivera, Herculano, Lanna, Cavalcante & Teixeira (2020: 15) and Anderson (2021: 205). Because there is an insufficient number of works in which the junior homonym was used over the preceding fifty years, the second condition of the reversal of precedence article is not met. As such, the principle of priority (ICZN Article 23.2) is to be applied, in that *Mantis lobata* Fabricius, 1798 is rendered permanently invalid and a new name is required. It should be noted that the senior homonym being transferred to *Harpagomantis* Kirby, 1899 and the junior homonym being later transferred to *Vates* is of no consequence to the homonymy of the two species, as the ICZN specifically defines a primary homonym as identical species-group names for different taxa originally combined with the same generic name.

Vates cayennensis **nomen novum**, a replacement name for the junior homonym *Mantis lobata* Fabricius, 1798.

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Figure 10: Holotype of *Mantis marginata* ♂ (left) with potential syntype (right). NHMD918190 & NHMD918204. Courtesy of Lars Vilhelmsen at the University of Copenhagen, Natural History Museum of Denmark Zoological Museum.

-marginata. Supplementum Entomologiae Systematicae, 1798: 191. Fabricius described *Mantis marginata* from a male specimen that he had received from Daldorff. He listed the type locality of this species as the “Isle de France” (Mauritius). Zimsen (1964: 12) tells us that Ingobert Karl Daldorff was a pupil of Fabricius who sent natural history specimens to Sehested & Tønder Lund as well as to Fabricius from his foreign stations— primarily those of India. The *marginata* holotype (Figure 10) remains within the Fabricius collection at the University of Copenhagen with a handwritten label that reads: “*Polyspilota marginata* F.” This label was created when the Kiel and Sehested-Tønder Lund collection were integrated together in Copenhagen, as evidenced by the fact that the genus *Polyspilota* was not established until 1838 by Burmeister— thirty years after Fabricius had died. A potential syntype to the holotype is present within the Fabricius collection. This specimen is without a label and is of a different species. It is unclear if Fabricius had involved this specimen within his original description of *marginata* or if the specimen was added to the collection after the fact.

Figure 11: Nontype of *Mantis marginata* ♂ NHMD67843. Courtesy of Lars Vilhelmsen at the University of Copenhagen, Natural History Museum of Denmark Zoological Museum.

A third specimen of *marginata* is also included within the Fabricius collection (Figure 11). This specimen has a typed label that reads: “Mantis marginata F. Ent. Syst. Suppl. 1798 p. 191,” which indicates the species determination and references the page number from Fabricius’ *Supplementum Entomologiae Systematicae*. This label was created when the Kiel and Copenhagen collections were integrated together in the 1960s into the first Zoological Museum. This specimen was part of the Sehested & Tønder Lund collection and is believed to have also been collected by Daldorff but was not part of Fabricius’ original description of *marginata*, which was based on the specimen that he had in his personal collection. Although Fabricius was well known to intentionally allocate duplicate specimens into different collections, including his own, in this case it would appear that the collector sent material to two different collectors (just as Zimsen noted). This species was described twenty years prior to Fabricius under the epithet *aeruginosa* Goeze, 1778 and has since been synonymized.

Polyspilota aeruginosa (Goeze, 1778)
= *Mantis marginata* Fabricius, 1798

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-mendica. *Systema Entomologiae*, 1775: 275. Fabricius noted that this specimen originated from “Alexandriae” (Alexandria, Egypt) and was part of the Forskål collection. Reid (2007: 78) noted that Peter Forskål (c. 1732-1763) was a favorite pupil of Linné who took part in a Danish expedition to Egypt and the Arabian peninsula, during which he succumbed to endemic fever. Carsten Niebuhr was reportedly the only survivor of this expedition and he returned to Denmark with some of the expedition’s collections. Fabricius described several insect species from these collections. The current whereabouts of this collection is unknown. Zimsen (1964: 615) documented that the *mendica* holotype is lost. In 1781, Fabricius republished the original description summary of *mendica* in *Species Insectorum*. He republished the description summary once more within *Mantissa Insectorum* in 1787 and again within *Entomologia Systematica* in 1793.

Blepharopsis mendica (Fabricius, 1775)
Mants mendica Fabricius, 1775

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Figure 12: Syntypes of *Mantis ministralis* (♀ left, ♂ center, ♀ right) with determination/reference label attached to drawer and collection locality label pinned to middle specimen. BMNH(E) #669469, 669470 & 669471. Joseph Banks collection at the Natural History Museum in London

-ministralis. *Systema Entomologiae*, 1775: 277-278. Fabricius described *Mantis ministralis* from a series of specimens that he had analyzed from the Banks collection. Fabricius noted that this species originated from “nova Hollandia” (New Holland or mainland Australia). These specimens represent the only known Mantodea that were collected during the voyage of the *Endeavour* when the ship made its first landfall in eastern Australia. As such, the specimens would have been collected between April and June 1770 under the direct supervision of Banks himself. The three syntypes within the Banks collection were evidently not separated by Fabricius and remain together to this day (Figure 12). The accompanying label reads: “*Mantis ministralis* Fab. Entom. p. 277. n. 18,” which indicates the species determination and references the page and species number from Fabricius’ *Systema Entomologiae*. An additional label that is pinned to the middle specimen has “Australia” inscribed and there is a smaller label attached to the drawer bottom with “Type” written on it. These labels are of an unknown hand and were evidently created through some curation process long after Solander and Banks had sorted the material from their voyage. In 1781, Fabricius republished the description summary of *ministralis* within *Species Insectorum*. He again published the description summary in 1787 within *Mantissa Insectorum* and once more within *Entomologia Systematica* in 1793.

Orthodera ministralis (Fabricius, 1775)
Mantis ministralis Fabricius, 1775

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Figure 13: Holotype of *Mantis monacha* ♂. NHMD67844. Courtesy of Lars Vilhelmsen at the University of Copenhagen, Natural History Museum of Denmark Zoological Museum.

-monacha. *Mantissa Insectorum*, 1787: 228. Fabricius described *Mantis monacha* from a male specimen that he had analyzed from the Sehested & Tønder Lund collection. He listed the type locality of this species as “Cap. Bon. Spei.” (the Cape of Good Hope or modern day Cape Town, South Africa). The *monacha* holotype (Figure 13) remains within the Fabricius collection at the University of Copenhagen with a typed label that reads: “*Mantis monacha* F. *Mant. Ins.* 1787 p. 228,” which indicates the species determination and references the page number from Fabricius’ *Mantissa Insectorum*. The collector of the holotype is unknown. In 1793, Fabricius republished the description summary of *monacha* within *Entomologia Systematica*.

Miomantis monacha (Fabricius, 1787)
Mantis monacha Fabricius, 1787

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Figure 14: Holotype of *Mantis nasuta* ♂. NHMD67845. Courtesy of Lars Vilhelmsen at the University of Copenhagen, Natural History Museum of Denmark Zoological Museum.

-nasuta. *Mantissa Insectorum*, 1787: 229. Fabricius described *Mantis nasuta* from a male specimen that he had analyzed from the Sehested & Tønder Lund collection. He listed the type locality of this species as “Cap. Bon. Spei.” (the Cape of Good Hope or modern day Cape Town, South Africa). The *nasuta* holotype (Figure 14) remains within the Fabricius collection at the University of Copenhagen with a typed label that reads: “Mantis nasuta F. Mant. Ins. 1787 p. 229,” which indicates the species determination and references the page number from Fabricius’ *Mantissa Insectorum*. This label was created when the Kiel and Copenhagen collections were integrated together in the 1960s into the first Zoological Museum. The collector of the holotype is unknown. Fabricius republished the description summary of this species within *Entomologia Systematica* in 1793.

Roy & Stiewe (2013: 28) pointed out that Thunberg had already used *Mantis nasuta* to describe an entirely different species in 1784— three years prior to Fabricius using this same name. As such, Fabricius’ name is invalid due to homonymy and is not available. This name was replaced by its first synonym that was introduced by Saussure in 1871.

Oxypilus (Anoxypilus) capensis (Saussure, 1871)
 = *Mantis nasuta* Fabricius, 1787

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Figure 15: Holotype of *Mantis obscura* ♂ with determination/reference label attached to drawer. Joseph Banks collection at the Natural History Museum in London

-obscura. Species Insectorum, 1781: 349. Fabricius described *Mantis obscura* from a male specimen that he had analyzed from the Banks collection. He listed the type locality of this species as “Africa aequinoctiali”. The holotype from the Banks collection has survived (Figure 15). The accompanying label reads: “Mant. Obscura F. Sp. Ins. n. 21,” which indicates the species determination and references the species number from Fabricius’ *Systema Insectorum*. There is a smaller label attached to the drawer bottom with “Type” written on it. These labels are of an unknown hand. In 1787, Fabricius republished the description summary of *obscura* within *Mantissa Insectorum* and once more within *Entomologia Systematica* in 1793.

Kirby unjustifiably assigned this species to *Carvilia* Stål, 1876 in 1904. In 1927, Giglio-Tos listed this species as *incertae sedis*. Fabricius’ original description matches the holotype quite well and from a limited digital analysis of this specimen, it is clear that it does not belong within *Carvilia* but is rather a member of *Deiphobe* Stål, 1877, in which case the type locality would be in error and this would represent another example of Fabricius erroneously recording an Indian species as having originated from Africa. As *obscura* was described very early on and is still considered valid, it is probable that it is a senior synonym to another *Deiphobe* species.

Deiphobe obscura (Fabricius, 1781) **comb. n.**

Mantis obscura Fabricius, 1781

Carvilia obscura (Fabricius, 1781)

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Figure 16: Holotype of *Mantis oculata* ♂ with determination/reference label attached to drawer and collection locality label pinned to specimen. BMNH(E) #669492. Joseph Banks collection at the Natural History Museum in London

-oculata. Species Insectorum, 1781: 348. Fabricius described *Mantis oculata* from a male specimen that he had analyzed from the Banks collection. He listed the type locality of this holotype as “Africa aequinoctiali”. This is apparently a recording error, as this species has been confidently assigned to *Schizocephala* Serville, 1831 and has been synonymized with *bicornis* Linné, 1758– a species that is precinctive to the Oriental region. Banks received regular shipments of specimens from both southern India and Sierra Leone during the decade leading up to Fabricius’ curation of his material. Thus, the mislabeling of some specimens could have easily occurred as this material was originally sorted. The holotype from the Banks collection has survived (Figure 16). The accompanying label reads: “Mant. Oculata Fabr. Sp. Ins. n. 16,” which indicates the species determination and references the species number from Fabricius’ *Systema Insectorum*. An additional label that is pinned to the specimen has “Africa” inscribed and there is a smaller label attached to the drawer bottom with “Type” written on it. These labels are of an unknown hand. In 1787, Fabricius republished the description summary of *oculata* within *Mantissa Insectorum* and once more within *Entomologia Systematica* in 1793.

Schizocephala bicornis (Linné, 1758)
Gryllus (Mantis) bicornis Linné, 1758
Mantis bicornis Linné, 1767
 = *Mantis oculata* Fabricius, 1781

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Figure 17: Syntype of *Mantis pauperata* ♀ with determination/reference label attached to drawer. Additional circular type label attached to the drawer was provided by the museum for cataloging. Joseph Banks collection at the Natural History Museum in London

-pauperata. *Species Insectorum*, 1781: 346-347. Fabricius described this species from two syntypes that derived from separate regions. One of the specimens originated from Coromandel (southeastern coastal region of India) and was retained within the Banks collection where Fabricius had sourced it (Figure 17). This specimen is missing its head capsule and one of its prothoracic legs but is believed to be female. The accompanying label reads: “Mant. Pauperata Fabr. Sp. Ins. n. 9,” which indicates the species determination and references the species number from Fabricius’ *Systema Insectorum*. This label is of an unknown hand. An additional green-ringed label that is attached to the drawer bottom reads “Type” and was provided for the museum by a subsequent curator. Anderson (2022: 31) advised that Stoll illustrated and described what he believed to be the conspecific male of this species in 1787. König most likely collected this specimen in southern India between 1778-1780.

Figure 18: Misidentified syntype of *Mantis pauperata* ♀ with Baillie label pinned to drawer. Additional typewritten label provided by University of Glasgow for cataloging. GLAHM: 133906 © The Hunterian, University of Glasgow 2023

The second syntype of *pauperata* (Figure 18) was listed by Fabricius as originating from Lusitania (Portugal/western Spain). It was reportedly collected by Gray and deposited into the Hunter collection. The accompanying Baillie label for this specimen reads “Mant. pauperata Fabr. pag 346 No. 9,” which refers to the page and species number from Fabricius’ *Species Insectorum*. We know from Robinson (2018) that Edward Whitaker Gray (c. 1746-1806) was Hunter’s pupil who sent him insect specimens from his hospital post in Portugal between 1773–1778. He was designated the “Keeper of Natural Curiosities at the British Museum”. Fabricius confused this female specimen from Portugal with Banks’ specimen from India, thinking that they were conspecific. The Portuguese specimen is actually a representative of *pennata*, a common European species that was not officially described until 1815 by Thunberg. In 1787, Fabricius republished the original description summary of *pauperata* within *Mantissa Insectorum* along with a description summary of the same species that Thunberg had provided in 1784. He republished the description summary once more within *Entomologia Systematica* in 1793. Lastly, the Fabricius collection at the University of Copenhagen contains a *Zoolea* Serville, 1839 specimen with a handwritten “*Vates pauperata*” label that was reportedly created when the collection was curated in the first Zoological Museum.

Empusa pauperata (Fabricius, 1781)
Mantis pauperata Fabricius, 1781

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Figure 19: Holotype of *Mantis perspicua* ♂. NHMD918246. Courtesy of Lars Vilhelmsen at the University of Copenhagen, Natural History Museum of Denmark Zoological Museum.

-perspicua. *Mantissa Insectorum*, 1787: 230. Fabricius described *Mantis perspicua* from a male specimen that he had received from von Rohr. He listed the type locality of this species as “Cajennae” (Cayenne, French Guiana). Zimsen (1964: 14) wrote that Julius von Rohr was “one of Fabricius’ most interested collectors”. He was dispatched by the Danish government to the Caribbean colonies of the Antilles and mainland South America to investigate the means of better cotton production. This trek began in 1783, whereupon von Rohr visited several islands of the Antilles before venturing into Colombia and the French colony of Cajennae. Zimsen reported that “from this journey he sent home large collections of insects”. Hopkins (2016: 133) tells us that von Rohr wrote an account of his expedition to South America, where he was reportedly accompanied by three local Amerindian guides and two black slaves of his own. Von Rohr detailed in this account that one of his slaves specialized in collecting insects. Thus, it would appear that some (possibly all) of the insect specimens that are attributed to von Rohr as the collector were actually obtained from nature by one of his supervised slaves. The specimens that von Rohr’s slave harvested from Cajennae were sent back to Denmark and became part of Fabricius’ personal collection. However, of the many different insects that were amassed during von Rohr’s expedition, there was only one Mantodea specimen, *Mantis perspicua*, that was received by Fabricius. In addition to the correspondence that von Rohr had with other European naturalists during his travels, he composed a hand-written journal of his personal encounters with nature while in St. Croix. This account only lists a single description and a corresponding illustration of one “*Mantis*” specimen, which was later determined to represent a Phasmid. Therefore, the only Mantodea record that we have of von Rohr’s entire collecting efforts is the single type specimen of *perspicua*. The *perspicua* holotype (Figure 19) remains within the Fabricius collection at the University of Copenhagen with a handwritten label that reads: “*Acontistes perspicuus* F.” This label was created when the Kiel and Sehested-Tønder Lund collection were integrated together in Copenhagen, as evidenced by the fact that the genus *Acontistes* was not established until 1838 by Burmeister— thirty years after Fabricius had died. In 1793, Fabricius republished the original description of this species within *Systema Entomologiae*.

Raptrix perspicua (Fabricius, 1787)
Mantis perspicua Fabricius, 1787

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-pulchra. Mantissa Insectorum, 1787: 229. Fabricius described *Mantis pulchra* from a specimen that he had analyzed from the Pflug collection. Johann Paul Gottfried Pflug (c. 1741-1789) was a medical doctor who collected natural history objects from abroad and sent them home to Denmark, where Fabricius assessed and described them. The type locality of this species was listed as “Tranquebariae” (now modern day Tharangambadi, India). The present location of the holotype is unknown. In 1793, Fabricius republished the original description of this species within *Entomologia Systematica* under “*pulcra*” –a misspelling of its epithet,

Euantissa pulchra (Fabricius, 1787)
Mantis pulchra Fabricius, 1787
Mantis pulcra Fabricius, 1793 *lapsus calami* of *pulchra* Fabricius, 1787

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Figure 20: Syntypes of *Mantis rustica* ♂ with determination/reference label attached to drawer and collection locality label pinned to left specimen. BMNH(E) #669455 & 669456. Joseph Banks collection at the Natural History Museum in London

-rustica. Species Insectorum, 1781: 350. Fabricius described *Mantis rustica* from two male specimens that he had analyzed from the Banks collection. He listed the type locality of this species as “littora Patagoniae” or the coast of Argentina. These specimens were likely collected by the Forster-Masson team during the first voyage of the *Resolution*. Another semiplausible theory concerning the provenance of the *rustica* syntypes is that they were collected under the direct supervision of Banks himself during the voyage of the *Endeavour*. The first landfall of this maiden voyage was near Rio de Janeiro, Brazil where the ship was temporarily impounded, which reportedly prevented Banks and Solander from harvesting any specimens. Once the *Endeavour* was released from impound, it made its way south and had its second stop within the Tierra del Fuego archipelago in southern Argentina. It was here that Banks and Solander collected their first known samples of natural history objects in Patagonia. However, if Banks did collect these specimens, it would be strange that Fabricius did not describe them in 1775, as he did with *ministralis*, when he first reviewed Banks’ material. Given that this species was not described until 1781, when Fabricius revisited the Banks collection to curate the new specimens that he

had received, it would follow that the *rustica* syntypes were added to the collection at a later time. Fortunately, the syntypes of *rustica* from the Banks collection have survived (Figure 20) and are available for study. One of the syntypes has had the genitalia previously prepared to confirm its generic placement. The accompanying label of these specimens reads: “Mant. Rustica F. Sp. Ins. n. 27,” which indicates the species determination and references the species number from Fabricius’ *Systema Insectorum*. An additional label that is pinned to the middle specimen has “Patagonia” inscribed and there is a smaller label attached to the drawer bottom with “Type” written on it. These labels are of an unknown hand. In 1787, Fabricius republished the description summary of *rustica* within *Mantissa Insectorum*. He again published the description summary within *Entomologia Systematica* in 1793.

Miobantia rustica (Fabricius, 1781)
Mantis rustica Fabricius, 1781

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Figure 21: Holotype of *Mantis sancta* ♀. Dorsal habitus (left) and closeup of pronotum (right) NHMD67847. Courtesy of Lars Vilhelmsen and Sree Gayathree Selvantharan at the University of Copenhagen, Natural History Museum of Denmark Zoological Museum.

-*sancta*. *Mantissa Insectorum*, 1787: 228. Fabricius described *Mantis sancta* from a female specimen that he had analyzed from the Schlanbusch collection. He listed the type locality of this species as “Gallia australiori” (southern France). Zimsen (1964: 14) tells us that Theodor Schlanbusch (c. 1756-1829) was an affluent magistrate who collected insects from southern Europe and India. His collection became part of the Sehested & Tønder Lund collection in Copenhagen, which contains many Fabricius types, and was later integrated with Fabricius’ personal collection from Kiel. The *sancta* holotype (Figure 21) remains within the Fabricius collection at the University of Copenhagen with a typed label that reads: “Mantis sancta F. Mant. Ins. 1 1787 p. 228,” which indicates the species determination and references the page number from Fabricius’ *Mantissa Insectorum*. This label was created when the Kiel and Copenhagen collections were integrated together in the 1960s.

Figure 22: Nontypes of *Mantis religiosa* ♂. NHMD918471 & NHMD918485. Courtesy of Lars Vilhelmsen at the University of Copenhagen, Natural History Museum of Denmark Zoological Museum.

Two additional males (Figure 22) have been found within the Fabricius collection at the University of Copenhagen with a handwritten label that reads: “*Mantis religiosa* L var. *sancta* F”. These specimens were evidently part of Fabricius’ personal collection in Kiel but were not described by him, as they were likely diagnosed as *religiosa*. They were subsequently designated as the *sancta* “variety” of *religiosa* when the collection was curated over one hundred and fifty years later. Fabricius never used the term “variety” and *sancta* was not associated with *religiosa* until after 1927. Thus, this label must have been created during the subsequent years between 1930-1970 when the Kiel and Sehested-Tønder Lund collection were integrated together in Copenhagen. In 1793, Fabricius republished the description summary of *sancta* within *Entomologia Systematica*.

Kirby unjustifiably assigned *sancta* to *Mantis* Linné, 1758 in 1904. In 1927, Giglio-Tos erroneously listed this species as a synonym of *religiosa* Linné, 1758, which it has been regarded as for the past century. The holotype of *sancta* possesses a much wider head capsule and pronotal morphology than what is found in *Mantis* and the habitus is significantly smaller than *religiosa*. The type locality of this specimen has evidently been incorrectly documented, as this species does not resemble any from the Mediterranean region. From a digital analysis of the holotype, in conjunction with Fabricius’ original description of the prothoracic legs having “two black points underneath,” it is clear that it does not belong within *Mantis* but is rather a member of *Miomantis* Saussure, 1870. This species is assuredly synonymous with another *Miomantis* species— most probably *monacha*— but it has not been used or treated as a valid name within the last century.

Miomantis sancta (Fabricius, 1787) **comb. n. nomen oblitum**
Mantis sancta Fabricius, 1787

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Figure 23: Holotype of *Mantis simulacrum* ♀. NHMD918232. Courtesy of Lars Vilhelmsen at the University of Copenhagen, Natural History Museum of Denmark Zoological Museum.

-*simulacrum*. *Entomologia Systematica*, 1793: 21. Fabricius described *Mantis simulacrum* from a female specimen that he had received from an unknown collector. He listed the type locality of this species as America, which seems to be incorrect. Anderson (2022: 47) erroneously reported that the type specimen for *simulacrum* has been lost. In fact, the *simulacrum* holotype (Figure 23) remains within the Fabricius collection at the University of Copenhagen with a handwritten label that reads: “*Mantis simulacrum* F.” This label was created when the Kiel and Sehested-Tønder Lund collection were integrated together in Copenhagen. This species has suffered considerable taxonomic confusion since its establishment and has been erroneously associated with *Parastagmatoptera* Saussure, 1871 and *Stagmomantis* Saussure, 1869 before being appropriately placed within *Hierodula* Burmeister, 1838. This species is assuredly synonymous with another *Hierodula* species— most probably *patellifera* Serville, 1839— but it has not been used or treated as a valid name within the last century.

Hierodula simulacrum (Fabricius, 1793) **nomen oblitum**
Mantis simulacrum Fabricius, 1793

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Figure 24: Holotype of *Mantis striata* ♀. NHMD918218. Courtesy of Lars Vilhelmsen at the University of Copenhagen, Natural History Museum of Denmark Zoological Museum.

-*striata*. *Entomologia Systematica*, 1793: 20. Fabricius described *Mantis striata* from a female specimen that he had received from Carlo Allioni (c. 1728-1804), the renown Italian physician and botanist. Fabricius listed the type locality of this species as Italy. The *striata* holotype (Figure 24) remains within the Fabricius collection at the University of Copenhagen with a handwritten label that reads: “*Mantis religiosa* L var. *striata* F.” This specimen was evidently part of Fabricius’ personal collection in Kiel. It was designated as the *striata* “variety” of *religiosa* when the collection was curated over one hundred and fifty years later. Fabricius never used the term “variety” and *striata* was not associated with *religiosa* until after 1927. Thus, this label must have been created during the subsequent years between 1930-1970 when the Kiel and Sehested-Tønder Lund collection were integrated together in Copenhagen.

Mantis religiosa Linné, 1758
= *Mantis striata* Fabricius, 1793

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Figure 25: Holotype of *Mantis superstitiosa* ♂ with determination/reference label attached to drawer and collection locality label pinned to specimen. Joseph Banks collection at the Natural History Museum in London

-*superstitiosa*. Species Insectorum, 1781: 348. Fabricius described *Mantis superstitiosa* from a male specimen that he had analyzed from the Banks collection. He listed the type locality of this holotype as “Africa aequinoctiali,” which would indicate that it was collected by Smeathman in Sierra Leone. The holotype from the Banks collection has survived (Figure 25). The accompanying label reads: “Mant. Superstitiosa F. Sp. Ins. n. 17,” which indicates the species determination and references the species number from Fabricius’ *Systema Insectorum*. There is a smaller label attached to the drawer bottom with “Type” written on it. These labels are of an unknown hand.

Figure 26: Probable syntypes of *Mantis superstitiosa* (♂ left, ♀ right) with mismatched Baillie label pinned to drawer of male specimen. Additional typewritten labels provided by University of Glasgow for cataloging. GLAHM: 133913 & GLAHM: 133742 © The Hunterian, University of Glasgow 2023

Figure 27: Probable syntypes of *Mantis superstitiosa* ♂. NHMD918274 & NHMD918288. Courtesy of Lars Vilhelmsen at the University of Copenhagen, Natural History Museum of Denmark Zoological Museum.

The Hunter collection currently contains two specimens of *superstitiosa* (Figure 26). These specimens are probable syntypes, given that Fabricius was prone to redistributing larger series of specimens into the cabinets of others while using Hunter’s museum as the primary depository of his designated duplicates. The mislabeled male specimen has an accompanying Baillie label that reads “Mant. Fenestrata Fabr. pag 349 No. 23,” which refers to the page and species number from Fabricius’ *Species Insectorum*. The female specimen is without a label. Two additional males (Figure 27) have been found within the Fabricius collection at the University of Copenhagen with a handwritten “*Tenodera superstitiosa*” label that was reportedly created when the collection was curated in the first Zoological Museum. In 1787,

Fabricius republished the description summary of *superstitiosa* within *Mantissa Insectorum* and once more within *Entomologia Systematica* in 1793.

Tenodera superstitiosa (Fabricius, 1781)
Mantis superstitiosa Fabricius, 1781

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-truncata. *Entomologia Systematica*, 1793: 17. Fabricius described *Mantis truncata* from a female specimen that he had examined from d’Orcy’s collection. He listed the type locality of this species as “Cajennae” (Cayenne, French Guiana). Jean Baptiste Francois Gigot d’Orcy was an affluent Parisian tax collector for King Louis XVI. We know from O’Gorman & Donald (2005) that through his wealth and influence, d’Orcy amassed a very large collection of natural history objects that were displayed within multiple cabinets that occupied several rooms of his home along with a substantial library of rare books. Additionally, d’Orcy used his wealth to employ several engravers and illustrators, publish a six-volume work on butterflies, fund the publications of other naturalists (such as Olivier), and finance several foreign expeditions that involved specimen collecting and illustration. Fabricius was known to have periodically resided in Paris throughout the later years of his life, during which time he visited d’Orcy’s home to examine his array of cabinets. The entirety of d’Orcy’s collection was later sold by his widow to the French state after he was guillotined in 1793 during the French Revolution. O’Gorman & Donald noted that d’Orcy’s insect cabinet was incorporated into the national collection, which is the present day Museum of Natural History in Paris. As is the case with several other species that display marked sexual dimorphism, Fabricius believed that this species was distinct but it was later determined to represent the conspecific female of *perspicua*.

Raptrix perspicua (Fabricius, 1787)
= *Mantis truncata* Fabricius, 1793

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Figure 28: Syntypes of *Mantis undata* ♂. NHMD67848 & NHMD67849. Courtesy of Lars Vilhelmsen at the University of Copenhagen, Natural History Museum of Denmark Zoological Museum.

-undata. *Entomologia Systematica*, 1793: 19. Fabricius described *Mantis undata* from two male specimens that he had analyzed from the Sehested & Tønder Lund collection. He listed the type locality of this species as “Tranquebariae” (now modern day Tharangambadi, India). The *undata* syntypes (Figure 28) remain within the Fabricius collection at the University of Copenhagen with a typed label that reads: “Mantis undata F. Ent. Syst. 2 1793 p. 19,” which indicates the species determination and references the page number from Fabricius’ *Entomologia Systematica*. This label was created when the Kiel and Copenhagen collections were integrated together in the 1960s. This species has been incorrectly associated with *Popa* Stal, 1856 for nearly two centuries. Given an examination of the syntypes, which perfectly match the original description provided by Fabricius, it is clearly evident that *undata* is synonymous with *Aethalochroa ashmoliana* (Westwood, 1841). Although the senior synonym *undata* has not been used as a valid name after 1899, the junior synonym has only been used in a few works by a handful of authors in the immediately preceding fifty years. Thus, both conditions of the ICZN Article 23.9 reversal of precedence clause are not met, which evokes the principle of priority of ICZN Article 23.2 and renders the younger name invalid.

Aethalochroa undata (Fabricius, 1793) **stat. rev. comb. n.**
Mantis undata Fabricius, 1793
 = *Aethalochroa ashmoliana* (Westwood, 1841) **n. syn.**

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-urbana. *Systema Entomologiae*, 1775: 278. Fabricius described *Mantis urbana* from a specimen that he had examined from the British Museum. He noted that this specimen derived from “Indiis”. This species commonly occurs in India at the present day, which gives further credence to *cancellata* representing *Asiadodis* Roy, 2004 rather than *Choeradodis*, as both specimens were very likely part of the original Sloane collection that exclusively sampled Old World colonies of the British Empire and no regions of South America. Zimsen (1964: 615) documented that the holotype is lost. In 1781, Fabricius republished the description summary of *urbana* within *Species Insectorum*. He again published the

description summary in 1787 within *Mantissa Insectorum* and once more within *Entomologia Systematica* in 1793.

Creobroter urbana (Fabricius, 1775)
Mantis urbana Fabricius, 1775

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Acknowledgements. My thanks and gratitude go out to Judith Marshall & Beulah Garner of the Natural History Museum, Jeanee Robinson of the University of Glasgow and Lars Vilhelmsen & Sree Gayathree Selvantharan of the University of Copenhagen for their invaluable assistance in locating type specimens within their respective institutions and providing images. As always, special thanks to Evgeny Shcherbakov for his invaluable feedback and assistance with this manuscript.

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To cite this article: Anderson, K. (2023): The Mantodea of Johan Fabricius. Soothsayer, Journal of Mantodea Research. 4 (1): 27-61.